

METHODOLOGY OF FORMATION OF CREATIVE SKILLS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE CLASSES

Ozotov Akbarjon Odiljon o'g'li

English teacher at the Academic Lyceum of the Tashkent State
University of Economics, Master at Webster University
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Abstract. Creative thinking in learning a foreign language is one of the biggest challenges of today. It has been proven that learning a foreign language through creative thinking is much easier. This article shows the methods, techniques, directions of teaching a foreign language to students through creative thinking and gives examples.

Keywords: Creative thinking, foreign language, student, method, task, ability, technique.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, a transition is being made from the theoretical foundations of the development of creativity to finding ways to develop creative abilities, and methods for the development of creativity are being developed. The nature of creative abilities has been revealed, the features, structure and criteria of creativity, factors influencing the development of creativity have been determined, however, the methods and techniques for the formation of creative abilities in students have not been sufficiently developed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For the development of students' creative abilities, the teacher must know the features and mechanisms of creativity formation, be able to identify students' creative abilities, their level of development, and also be able to determine learning paths aimed at developing students' creative abilities¹.

The concept of creativity has been around for a long time. The Greek philosopher Plato in ancient times argued that a person must be creative. Thus, the word "creativity" was already known in ancient times.

The term "creativity" comes from the Latin word, which means "creation". This concept refers to the ability of a person to generate unusual ideas. The word "create" comes from the Latin "creatus, creatura", which translates as "creation". Thus, the word "creativity" has a Latin origin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

American psychologist E.P. Torrance argued that creativity refers to increased sensitivity to problems, actions to identify these problems and search

¹ Druzhinin V.N. Psychology of general abilities / V.N. Druzhinin. - St. Petersburg: Piter, 2012. - 368 p.

for their solutions, i.e. creativity is the ability of a person to generate a large number of non-standard ideas in any field of activity.

Abraham Maslow, the founder of "humanistic psychology", defined creativity as a creative orientation that is innately characteristic of everyone, but lost by the majority under the influence of the existing system of education and retained only by a select group of carriers of the highest achievements.

Creativity is usually studied in two directions. In the first direction, creativity is considered depending on intelligence, i.e. depending on cognitive (cognitive) processes.

Since the beginning of the 20th century, it has been believed that creativity is directly related to intelligence. By the middle of the 20th century, an opinion appeared that creativity was in no way connected with intelligence. At the same time, the term "creativity", this led to various studies in the field of creativity. Based on the results of the researches, the following conclusions were drawn:

- 1) there are no creative abilities as such;
- 2) creative ability (creativity) is an independent factor, independent of intelligence;
- 3) a high level of intelligence development implies a high level of creative abilities and vice versa.

Also, creativity can be considered as the creative abilities of an individual, as the ability to generate unusual ideas, deviate from traditional patterns of thinking, and quickly solve problem situations. In the presented definition, creativity is defined as a person's susceptibility to any new ideas.

A foreign language is a general educational subject. When learning a foreign language, students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities, broaden their general educational horizons, develop personal qualities, moral values, attitudes and beliefs. At the lessons of a foreign language, it is necessary to form and develop the creativity of students, i.e. to form and develop in students the ability to think outside the box and make unusual decisions. In the educational process, the task of the teacher is the development of students, the development of their creativity and, in general, the education of the individual².

The development of students' creativity in foreign language lessons is more effective if the following conditions are taken into account:

1. The teacher is competent and has a high level of professional excellence.
2. Creation of a favorable socio-psychological climate in a foreign language lesson.

² Torrance, E. Guiding creative talent - Englewood Cliffs / E. Torrance. - W.J. : Prentice Hall, 2014. - p. 160.

3. Use of tasks and exercises of different levels complexity depending on the individual and age characteristics of students and their creative, intellectual and physical abilities.

4. Pedagogical methods, techniques and forms of teaching a foreign language correspond to the personal and age characteristics of students.

Instruction for students: Work in the groups, write your associations to the topic "A choice of career". Try to write more associations as you can³.

Student responses: find out interests, talents and ambitions, parents' advice, friends' advice, someone's advice, follow in someone's footsteps, to be encouraged by teachers, take a long time to make up their minds, to change their minds many times, an abundance of choices, a professional career choice test, not a random job, help to define future profession, interesting job, difficult choice, uncertainty, satisfying job, to choose.

Results:

Students actively worked in groups, discussed in different directions on the topic of choosing a profession. The students tried to write as many associations as possible on the topic of choosing a profession, actively used the studied words and expressions on the topic. In both groups, associations were sometimes repeated. Students using associations expressed their opinion on the topic of choosing a profession.

CONCLUSION

In our article, we considered the problem of the formation of students' creativity in a foreign language lesson. The purpose of our study was to create and test a set of methods and techniques aimed at developing the creativity of students in a foreign language lesson. We have set and solved the following tasks:

1. To study the psychological and pedagogical literature on the problem of the formation of creativity in students of an educational institution.
2. Determine the content and structure of creativity.
3. Create a set of methods and techniques aimed at shaping the creativity of students in a foreign language lesson.
4. To test a set of methods and techniques aimed at shaping the creativity of students in a foreign language lesson.

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³ Ermolaeva-Tomina L. B. Experimental study of creative abilities / L.B. Ermolaeva-Tomina / Questions of psychology. - 2017. - No. 4. - P. 74-84.

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